

Verb sense classification

Only the names of the verb senses classified as non-agentive in our study (and their superordinates) are reproduced below. The full classification can be found in Faber and Mairal (1999: 279-293)¹. Note that the verbs in square brackets are those originally appearing as examples in Faber and Mairal's classification. Nevertheless, this does not necessarily imply that these verbs were classified as such in our study, since they may more frequently activate a different sense in the corpus used.

Non-agentive verb sense

Intransitive verb sense

Agentive verb sense

1. EXISTENCE

1.1. [...]

1.2. [...]

1.2.1. [...]

1.3. [...]

1.3.1. [...]

1.4. [...]

1.4.1. [...]

1.4.1.1. [...]

1.4.1.2. [...]

1.4.1.3. [...]

1.5. **To exist as something**

1.5.1. **To exist as the representation of something else [represent, express]**

1.5.1.1. [...]

1.5.2. **To exist as a part of something [comprise, constitute]**

1.6. [...]

1.6.1. [...]

1.6.1.1. [...]

1.6.2. [...]

1.6.3. [...]

1.6.3.1. [...]

1.7. [...]

1.7.1. [...]

1.8. [...]

1.8.1. [...]

1.8.2. [...]

1.8.2.1. [...]

1.8.2.2. [...]

1.8.2.3. [...]

2. MOVEMENT

2.1. **General [move, go, come]**

2.1.1. [...]

¹ Pamela Faber and Ricardo Mairal. 1999. *Constructing a Lexicon of English Verbs*. Mouton de Gruyter, Berlin.

- 2.1.1.1. [...]
- 2.1.1.1.1. [...]
- 2.1.1.2. [...]
- 2.1.1.2.1. [...]
- 2.1.1.3. [...]
- 2.1.1.4. [...]
- 2.1.1.4.1. [...]
- 2.1.1.5. [...]
- 2.1.1.6. [...]
- 2.1.1.6.1. [...]
- 2.1.1.7. [...]
- 2.1.1.7.1. [...]
- 2.1.1.8. [...]
- 2.1.1.8.1. [...]
- 2.1.2. [...]
- 2.1.2.1. [...]
- 2.1.2.1.1. [...]
- 2.1.2.1.1.1. [...]
- 2.1.3. To move towards a place [go, travel, advance]
- 2.1.3.1. [...]
- 2.1.3.2. To move towards a common point, coming together [meet, join, gather]
- 2.1.3.2.1. [...]
- 2.1.3.3. [...]
- 2.1.3.3.1. [...]
- 2.1.3.4. [...]
- 2.1.3.4.1. [...]
- 2.1.3.5. [...]
- 2.1.3.5.1. [...]
- 2.1.4. To move across [cross]
- 2.1.5. To move over/through [pass, clear]
- 2.1.5.1. [...]
- 2.1.6. [...]
- 2.1.6.1. [...]
- 2.1.7. [...]
- 2.1.8. To move in relation to somebody/something
- 2.1.8.1. To move together [accompany]
- 2.1.8.1.1. [...]
- 2.1.8.1.2. [...]
- 2.1.8.1.3. [...]
- 2.1.8.1.4. To move with somebody, going after/behind [follow]
- 2.1.8.2. [...]
- 2.1.8.2.1. [...]
- 2.1.8.3. To move slower in relation to somebody/something [lag, trail]
- 2.1.8.4. To move towards and beyond somebody/ something [pass]
- 2.1.8.5. To move round in order to be on all sides of [surround, circle]
- 2.1.8.6. [...]
- 2.1.8.6.1. [...]

- 2.1.8.6.2. [...]
 - 2.1.8.6.2.1. [...]
 - 2.1.8.6.2.2. [...]
 - 2.1.8.6.2.2.1. [...]
- 2.1.8.7. [...]
- 2.1.8.7.1. [...]
- 2.1.8.8. To move into a place [enter]
 - 2.1.8.8.1. [...]
 - 2.1.8.8.2. [...]
- 2.1.8.9. [...]
- 2.1.8.10. To move to a different place/position [change, switch, transfer]
 - 2.1.8.10.1. [...]
 - 2.1.8.10.2. [...]
 - 2.1.8.10.3. [...]
- 2.1.9. To not move any more, after having moved [stop, halt]
 - 2.1.9.1. [...]
- 2.2. Liquid**
 - 2.2.1. [...]
 - 2.2.1.1. [...]
 - 2.2.1.2. [...]
 - 2.2.1.2.1. [...]
 - 2.2.1.3. [...]
 - 2.2.1.3.1. [...]
 - 2.2.1.3.2. [...]
 - 2.2.2. [...]
 - 2.2.2.1. [...]
 - 2.2.2.2. [...]
 - 2.2.3. [...]
 - 2.2.3.1. [...]
 - 2.2.3.2. [...]
 - 2.2.4. [...]
 - 2.2.4.1. [...]
- 2.3. Atmosphere**
 - 2.3.1. [...]
 - 2.3.2. [...]
 - 2.3.2.1. [...]
 - 2.3.3. [...]
 - 2.3.4. [...]
- 2.4. Land**
 - 2.4.1. [...]
 - 2.4.1.1. [...]
 - 2.4.1.1.1. [...]
 - 2.4.1.1.2. [...]
 - 2.4.1.2. [...]
 - 2.4.2. [...]
 - 2.4.3. [...]
 - 2.4.3.1. [...]
 - 2.4.3.2. [...]

2.4.3.3. [...]

2.4.3.4. [...]

3. POSITION (to be in a particular/state/condition/position without moving/changing)

3.1. To be in a particular/state/condition/position without moving/changing [stay, lie]

3.1.1. [...]

3.1.1.1. [...]

3.1.1.1.1. [...]

3.1.1.1.2. [...]

3.1.1.1.3. [...]

3.1.1.1.4. [...]

3.1.1.1.4.1. [...]

3.1.1.1.4.2. [...]

3.1.1.1.5. [...]

3.1.1.1.6. [...]

3.1.1.1.7. [...]

3.1.1.1.8. [...]

3.1.1.1.9. [...]

4. CONTACT

4.1. To come into contact with somebody/something [hit]

4.1.1. [...]

4.1.2. [...]

4.1.3. [...]

4.1.3.1. [...]

4.1.4. To not hit [miss]

5. CHANGE (to begin to be different)

5.1. To become [change]

5.1.1. [...]

5.1.2. [...]

5.1.2.1. [...]

5.1.3. [...]

5.1.3.1. [...]

5.1.4. [...]

5.1.4.1. [...]

5.1.4.2. [...]

5.1.4.3. [...]

5.1.4.4. [...]

5.1.5. [...]

5.1.5.1. [...]

5.1.5.2. [...]

5.1.5.3. [...]

5.1.6. [...]

5.1.6.1. [...]

5.1.7. [...]

- 5.1.7.1. [...]
- 5.1.7.1.1. [...]
- 5.1.7.2. [...]
- 5.1.7.2.1. [...]
- 5.1.7.3. [...]
- 5.1.7.3.1. [...]
- 5.1.8. [...]
- 5.1.8.1. [...]

6. PERCEPTION (to become aware of the existence of somebody/ something)

6.1. General perception (all senses): to become aware [perceive, find, discover]

6.2. Visual perception (To become aware by using one's eyes) [see, look]

- 6.2.1. To see [notice, observe]
- 6.2.2. To see intentionally [distinguish, discern]
- 6.2.3. [...]
- 6.2.3.1. [...]
- 6.2.4. [...]
- 6.2.4.1. [...]
- 6.2.4.2. [...]
- 6.2.5. [...]

6.3. Olfactory perception (To become aware through one's nose) [smell, scent]

- 6.3.1. To cause somebody to become aware of something through one's nose [smell, stink]

6.4. Auditory perception (To become aware through one's ears)

- 6.4.1. To perceive something with one's ears [hear]
- 6.4.2. To hear intentionally [listen]

6.5. [...]

7. COGNITION (to become aware through one's mind) [know]

7.1. To become aware of something, (having it) in one's mind [know]

- 7.1.1. To come to know something [learn]
 - 7.1.1.1. To cause somebody to learn [teach]
 - 7.1.1.2. To cause something to be known [show]
- 7.1.2. To know the nature/meaning of something [understand]
 - 7.1.2.1. [...]
 - 7.1.2.2. To cause something to be understood better [clarify]
 - 7.1.2.3. To understand with difficulty [grasp]
 - 7.1.2.4. To not understand [mistake]
 - 7.1.2.4.1. [...]

7.2. To use one's mind to become (more) aware of something in a certain way [think about]

- 7.2.1. To think about something bringing it back into one's mind from the past [remember]
- 7.2.2. To think about something that has happened in the past [reflect]
- 7.2.3. To think about something (usu. in order to understand it better [meditate])
- 7.2.4. To think about something in order to make a decision (in the future)

- [consider]
- 7.3. To use one's mind to form an opinion/idea [think (of)]**
 - 7.3.1. To think something, having formed an opinion/come to a decision about it [decide]
 - 7.3.2. To think something is true [believe]
 - 7.3.3. To think something is going to happen [expect]
 - 7.3.4. To think something is likely to be true [suppose]
 - 7.3.5. To think without knowing if it is true [guess]
 - 7.3.6. To think something may not be true [doubt]
 - 7.3.7. To think (of) something, forming it in one's mind as an idea/picture [imagine]
- 8. FEELING (to become aware of something other than by sight, having a sensation)**
 - 8.1. [...]**
 - 8.1.1. [...]
 - 8.2. To feel something good [enjoy]**
 - 8.3. [...]**
 - 8.3.1. [...]
 - 8.4. To feel happiness [delight in, thrill, rejoice]**
 - 8.4.1. [...]
 - 8.5. To feel aversion [dislike, hate, detest]**
 - 8.5.1. [...]
 - 8.5.2. [...]
 - 8.6. To feel attraction [like, love, admire]**
 - 8.6.1. [...]
 - 8.6.2. [...]
 - 8.6.2.1. [...]
 - 8.7. To feel something bad in one's body [hurt, ache]**
 - 8.7.1. [...]
 - 8.7.2. [...]
 - 8.8. To feel fear [fear, dread, worry]**
 - 8.8.1. [...]
 - 8.8.1.1. [...]
 - 8.9. To feel surprise [wonder, marvel]**
 - 8.9.1. [...]
 - 8.10. [...]**
 - 8.10.1.1. [...]
 - 8.11. To feel a need to do something or to have/get something [want, wish, desire]**
- 9. SPEECH [say, speak, talk]**
 - 9.1. To say something in a particular way**
 - 9.1.1. To say something formally [address, state, declare]
 - 9.1.2. To say something informally [gossip, chat]
 - 9.1.3. To say something firmly [insist, emphasize]
 - 9.1.4. To say something precisely [specify]
 - 9.1.5. To say something briefly [mention]

- 9.1.6. To say something again [repeat]
- 9.1.7. To say something with difficulty [stutter, stammer]
- 9.1.8. To say something quickly/continuously [chatter, babble]
- 9.1.9. To say something suddenly/loudly [exclaim, shout]
- 9.1.10. To say something in a soft way [whisper]
- 9.1.11. To say something angrily [snarl]
- 9.1.12. To say something unhappily in a dissatisfied way [complain, lament]
- 9.1.13. To say something in a proud way [boast, brag]
- 9.1.14. [...]

9.2. To say something

- 9.2.1. [...]
 - 9.2.1.1. [...]
 - 9.2.1.2. To say that something is true [acknowledge, admit]
 - 9.2.1.2.1. To say that something will happen [foretell, predict]
 - 9.2.1.2.2. To say that something is certain [promise, guarantee]
 - 9.2.1.3. To say positive things about somebody/something
 - 9.2.1.3.1. [...]
 - 9.2.1.3.2. To say positive things, saying that something should be considered [suggest, advise]
- 9.2.2. To say something is not the case (negative things)
 - 9.2.2.1. To say no to somebody/something [refuse, reject]
 - 9.2.2.2. [...]
 - 9.2.2.2.1. [...]
 - 9.2.2.3. To say something bad may happen [warn, threaten]
- 9.2.3. To say something without knowing if it is the case [guess]

9.3. To say something for a particular purpose/with a specific result

- 9.3.1. To say something to somebody so that they will do it [direct, order]
 - 9.3.1.1. To say something to somebody else to put an idea in their mind [suggest]
- 9.3.2. To say something in order to get something else [ask, request]
 - 9.3.2.1. To say something in question form in order to get an answer [ask, question]
 - 9.3.2.1.1. To say something in return to something [answer]
 - 9.3.2.1.2. To say something not in return to something [remark, comment]
- 9.3.3. To say something to somebody to tell them about it
 - 9.3.3.1. To say something expressing an opinion or judgement one has arrived at [reason]
 - 9.3.3.2. [...]
 - 9.3.3.3. [...]
 - 9.3.3.4. To say something to somebody giving an account of it [describe]
 - 9.3.3.5. To say the main points of [outline]
 - 9.3.3.6. To say something to somebody else, talking it over from several points of view [discuss]

9.4. [...]

9.5. [...]

10. SOUND

10.1. [...]

- 10.1.1. [...]
 - 10.1.1.1. [...]
 - 10.1.1.2. [...]
 - 10.1.1.3. [...]
 - 10.1.1.3.1. [...]
 - 10.1.1.3.2. [...]
 - 10.1.1.3.3. [...]
- 10.1.2. [...]
 - 10.1.2.1. [...]
 - 10.1.2.1.1. [...]
 - 10.1.2.2. [...]
 - 10.1.2.2.1. [...]
 - 10.1.2.2.2. [...]
 - 10.1.2.2.3. [...]
 - 10.1.2.3. [...]
- 10.1.3. [...]
 - 10.1.3.1. [...]
 - 10.1.3.2. [...]
 - 10.1.3.3. [...]
 - 10.1.3.4. [...]

10.2. [...]

10.3. [...]

- 10.3.1. [...]
- 10.3.2. [...]
- 10.3.3. [...]
- 10.3.4. [...]
- 10.3.5. [...]
 - 10.3.5.1. [...]
 - 10.3.5.2. [...]
- 10.3.6. [...]
- 10.3.7. [...]

11. LIGHT

11.1. [...]

- 11.1.1. [...]
- 11.1.2. [...]
- 11.1.3. [...]
- 11.1.4. [...]
- 11.1.5. [...]

11.2. [...]

12. POSSESSION

12.1. To have something [possess, own, hold]

- 12.1.1. To come to have something [get, obtain]
 - 12.1.1.1. [...]
 - 12.1.1.2. [...]

12.1.1.3. To get something after it has been given/sent to you [receive]

12.1.1.4. [...]

12.1.1.5. [...]

12.1.2. To continue to have something [keep, save]

12.1.2.1. To have something within as a part [contain, include]

12.1.2.2. [...]

12.1.2.2.1. [...]

12.1.3. To stop having [lose]

12.1.3.1. [...]

12.1.4. [...]

12.1.4.1. [...]

12.1.4.2. [...]

12.1.4.3. [...]

12.1.4.4. [...]

12.1.4.5. [...]

12.1.4.6. [...]

12.1.4.7. [...]

12.1.4.8. [...]

12.1.4.9. [...]

12.2. To not have [lack]

13. ACTION

13.1. [...]

13.1.1. [...]

13.1.2. [...]

13.1.3. [...]

13.1.4. [...]

13.1.5. [...]

13.1.6. [...]

13.1.7. [...]

13.1.7.1. [...]

13.1.7.1.1. [...]

13.1.8. [...]

13.2. To not do something [fail, neglect]

13.2.1. [...]

13.3. [...]

13.4. [...]

13.5. [...]

13.5.1. [...]

13.5.2. [...]

13.5.3. [...]

13.5.4. [...]

13.5.4.1. [...]

13.5.4.2. [...]

13.5.4.3. [...]

13.5.4.3.1. [...]

13.5.4.4. [...]

13.5.4.5. [...]

13.6. [...]

- 13.6.1. [...]
- 13.6.2. [...]
- 13.6.3. [...]
- 13.6.4. [...]
- 13.6.5. [...]